

**ОБОСНОВАНИЕ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ПАТОЛОГИИ ПОЛОСТИ РТА У ДЕТЕЙ И
ПОДРОСТКОВ С ДЕТСКИМ ЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНЫМ ПАРАЛИЧОМ С ПОМОЩЬЮ КЛИНИКО-
ЛАБОРАТОРНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ**

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**BASING THE FORMATION OF PATHOLOGIES OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN CHILDREN AND
ADOLESCENTS WITH CEREBRAL PALSY WITH THE HELP OF CLINICAL AND LABORATORY
STUDIES**

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АННОТАЦИЯ

У детей и подростков с детским церебральным параличом формирование патологических изменений в органах и тканях полости рта и дисбаланс компенсаторно-приспособительных механизмов в организме, в том числе негативное состояние образования свободных радикалов, может вызывать «окислительный стресс» в клеточной мембране. Цель исследования. Заключается в оценке физиолого-биохимических характеристик ротовой жидкости в полости рта у детей и подростков с детским церебральным параличом и анализе ее значения в формировании стоматологических заболеваний. Материалы и методы. Проведено комплексное клиничко-стоматологическое и лабораторное исследование 299 детей и подростков, в том числе 6–9 лет (102); 10–13 лет (100); 14–18 лет (97). По полу мальчиков было 168, девочек 131, из них 143 с детским церебральным параличом в основной группе и 156 пациентов в контрольной группе без соматической патологии. Изучены важнейшие биохимические показатели: провоспалительные и противовоспалительные цитокины, интерлейкины, активность супероксиддисмутазы, прооксидантная и антиоксидантная системы, перекисное окисление липидов, содержание кальция и фосфора, вязкость ротовой жидкости, буферная емкость. Результаты. Отрицательное состояние в системе, регулирующей гомеостаз в ротовой жидкости, обуславливает увеличение числа стоматологических заболеваний, и наоборот - интегральная связь процесса между патологическими изменениями ферментативных и низкомолекулярных звеньев антиоксидантной системы. Ротовая жидкость и нарушения минерального обмена, и полученные результаты показывают, что в ротовой жидкости в полости рта статистически подтверждены отрицательные изменения связи иммунной системы с генетикой, особенно в старших возрастных группах. Заключение. Таким образом, у детей и подростков с детским церебральным параличом окислительный стресс и отрицательные изменения иммунной системы в генетической и органической связи с развитием и тяжестью стоматологических заболеваний подтверждают достоверность полученных результатов.

ABSTRACT

Objective. Among children and adolescents with cerebral palsy, the formation of pathological changes in the organs and tissues of the oral cavity and an imbalance in compensatory-adaptive mechanisms in the body, including a negative state in the formation of free radicals, can cause "oxidative stress" in the cell membrane. The purpose of the study. It consists of evaluating the physiological and biochemical characteristics of the oral fluid in the oral cavity among children and adolescents with cerebral palsy and analyzing its significance in the formation of dental diseases. Materials and methods. A comprehensive clinical-dental and laboratory study was conducted on 299 children and adolescents, including 6–9 years old (102); 10–13 years old (100); and 14–18-year-olds (97). By gender, there were 168 boys and 131 girls, 143 of whom had cerebral palsy in the main group and 156 patients in

the control group without somatic pathology. The most important biochemical indicators were studied: pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines, interleukins, superoxide dismutase activity, prooxidant and antioxidant systems, lipid peroxidation, calcium and phosphorus content, oral fluid viscosity, and buffer capacity. Results. A negative state in the system that regulates homeostasis in the oral fluid causes an increase in the number of dental diseases, and vice versa-an integral connection of the process between pathological changes in the enzymatic and low molecular units of the antioxidant system. Oral fluid and mineral metabolism disorders, and the results show that oral fluid in the oral cavity has statistically confirmed negative changes in the connection of the immune system to genetics, especially in older age groups. Conclusion. Thus, among children and adolescents with cerebral palsy, oxidative stress and negative changes in the immune system in genetic and organic connection with the development and severity of dental diseases confirm the reliability of the results.

Ключевые слова: ротовая жидкость, слюна, биохимический состав слюны, детский церебральный паралич, стоматологические заболевания.

Keywords: oral fluid, saliva, biochemical composition of saliva, cerebral palsy, dental diseases.

Introduction. A number of authors have emphasized that children with cerebral palsy need special medical, especially dental care [1]. Currently, the clinic of dental diseases among children with cerebral palsy has been sufficiently studied, however, the etiology of dental diseases, and the mechanisms of their formation are not explained at the level of hypotheses and assumptions; including some researchers that pathologies in the facial-jaw system and oral cavity organs and tissues in children with cerebral palsy are related to the stage of the central nervous system in the perinatal period, other researchers the intensity of dental diseases in children with cerebral palsy and emphasized its uniqueness with heavy forms [2,3]. It is also an important factor to confirm that the organs and tissues of the oral cavity are a single fluid - the oral cavity is a single system with its mixed fluid, the breakdown of lipids and starches under the influence of endogenous enzymes, and the fact that the salivary composition of the oral cavity is an indicator of the result of local and general diseases [4,5]. For example, it has been noted that in the etiopathogenesis and formation of cerebral palsy, the abnormality of oxidation and release of free radicals, unfavorable changes in the composition of macroorganisms, as well as in the pro- and antioxidant system, as well as in the example of oral cavity fluid are observed [6,7]. In conclusion, the delay in the oxidation process confirms the importance of neurological deficiency and damage to the organs of the oral cavity, and vice versa, the formation of pathologies, therefore, the study of pathobiochemical mechanisms, nosological diagnosis, pathogenetic treatment and the prevention of relapse complications are the guarantee of promising achievements [8,9].

The aim of the study is to analyze the importance of oral fluid in the formation of dental diseases by evaluating the physiological and biochemical properties of the oral fluid in the oral cavity among children and adolescents with cerebral palsy.

Materials and methods.

To carry out our research, 299 children and adolescents underwent clinical-dental, clinical-laboratory and clinical-functional examinations; those in research - by age; 6-9 years old (34.1%); 10-13 years old (33.4%); and 14-18 years old (32.4%) groups; by gender - 168 (56.2%) boys and 131 (44.1%) girls. Including - 143 (main group (MG)) children and adolescents with cerebral palsy - 44 (30.8%) 6-9 years old (MG-1; -28 boys; -16 girls); 39 (27.27%) 10-13 years old (MG-

2; -25 boys; -14 girls); - 60 (41.9%) 14-18-year-olds (MG- 3; -30 boys; -30 girls), i.e., mentally retarded patients of cerebral palsy: Control group (CG) - 156 people; including - 58 (37.17%) 6-9 years old (CG-1; -31 boys, - 27 girls); 61 (39.1%) 10-13 years old (CG-2; -33 boys, - 28 girls); and 37 (23.7%) 14-18-year-old (CG-3; - 21 boys, -16 girls) somatically healthy children and adolescents, but in need of dental rehabilitation, participated in the study.

Biochemical characteristics of oral fluid unstimulated secretory saliva composition; the concentration of interleukin IL-1, IL-2, IL-4, important anti-inflammatory cytokines in the activity of the local immune system, was studied. IL-8, IL-10, immunoenzymes (IE) were analyzed using the equipment and devices of "Vector-Best" and Thermo Fisher Scientific, and the results were anti-inflammatory cytokines - IL-1; IL-2; IL-8 and inflammatory cytokines (IC) IL-4; IL-10 was expressed in conditional units (Shar/b) and ng/l.: Superoxide dismutase activity Kostyuka V.A. determined by the method; also Korolyuk M.A. the additional integral coefficient of oxidative modification of biomolecules was calculated for the functional state of anti-inflammatory cytokines using the colorimetric method; The degree of lipid peroxidation in OS was assessed by thiobarbituric acid 2-type lipid product peroxidation. The study material was obtained from the morning fasting study group; - calcium (Ca), phosphorus (P), pH-level in oral fluid, viscosity, buffer capacity, mineral exchange were also evaluated. Materials obtained during the research Excel MC Office 2013. Statistical analysis was performed using the parametric Students t-test or the non-parametric U-test using the program [10,11].

Results and its discussion.

Among children and adolescents with cerebral palsy, the level of unstimulated secretion of saliva decreased by 1.6 times compared to the control group and averaged $0.27 \pm 0.03^*$ ml/min. A number of literatures have emphasized that the course of dental diseases among children and adolescents with cerebral palsy is manifested in intensive and clinically severe features [12]. Against the background of a decrease in the salivary index of unstimulated secretion, "incorrect hypersalivation" was formed in cerebral palsy, oral cavity and anatomical-functional disorders of the lips - dysphagia, negative changes in the activity of the muscles around the mouth - hypofunction, pathology of the bite, the shape of the palate, dysfunction of the autonomic nervous system, etc. were observed [13].

In children and adolescents with cerebral palsy (MG) - a decrease in Ca concentration was observed: while the indicators in the table remained unchanged among young groups in the control group, MG-1 - 64.8±9.29; MG-2 - 75.3±10.92; MG-3 was 78.4±3.22.

At the same time, differences in the age range; 6-9 years; - 10-13 years and 14-18 years in CG and between MG was less significant compared to CG-1 and CG- 2, and compared to CG-3 - showed a smaller decrease in Ca (Table 1).

Table 1.

Indicators of oral fluid mineral metabolism and physicochemical properties in the study group.

Indicator	Clinical group (M ± σ)							
	Average MG	MG-1	MG -2	MG -3	Average CG	CG-1	CG -2	CG -3
NSS, ml/min	0,27±0,03*	0,24±0,04	0,22±0,08	0,33±0,02	0,40±0,07	0,36±0,1	0,40±0,04	0,43±0,09
Ca, mg/l	31,8±4,23*	35,9 ± 5,07*	31,1 ± 4,38*,#	28,5±3,05	72,8±6,32	64,8 ± 9,29	75,3±10,92^	78,4±3,22
P, mg/l	89,3±9,02*	108,2±12,01*	84,5±10,06*,#	75,2±8,04	151,8±15,82	140,5±16,82	152,1±17,7^	162,8±16,28
Ca/P, additional unit	0,48±0,5*	0,33 ± 0,06*	0,37 ± 0,07*	0,58±0,04	0,51±0,09	0,46 ± 0,09	0,50 ± 0,11	0,68±0,86
Viscosity, relative unit	3,01±0,48*	2,28±0,268*	3,08±0,46*,#	3,68±0,46*,#	2,33±0,422	2,14±0,482	2,28±0,280	2,48±0,420
pH, supplementary unit	6,34±0,44*	6,88±0,513*	6,28±0,445*,#	5,86±0,324*,#	6,55±0,344	7,01±0,389	6,44±0,458^	6,22±0,228^
Buffer capacity, ball/p	2,9±0,24*	3,4±0,44*	2,9±0,66*,#	2,46±0,14*,#	4,0±0,30	4,6±0,30	4,2±0,48^	3,2±0,48^

Note: * - p<0.05 compared to the CG index in the age range; ^-p<0.05 compared to the CG-1 group; # - p<0.05 compared to the MG-1 group indicator; d.e. - unit contributions; Ca - calcium; P is phosphorus.

It should be noted that in children and adolescents with cerebral palsy, the amount of oral saliva - P decreased sharply compared to the control group (89.3±9.02*; 151.8±15.82 ratio); also significant pathological changes in the main group depending on the age group - the amount of P increased by 12.8%, unlike the control group, as they grew older - the amount of P decreased sharply by 35.5%; this condition is confirmed by the sinking phenomenon, which increases the loss of biologically active components of the stomach, which are involved in many physiologically important functions at the local level in children and adolescents with cerebral palsy: - the lack of P not only decreases the remineralization activity of the oral fluid but also the balance of the ion content, which including the buffer system - dihydrogen and hydrophosphate ions is characterized by difficulty in synthesis. Clinically, the process is reflected in swallowing disorder, involuntary flow of oral fluid, caries Index increase, inflammatory processes in local tissues increase [14].

Significant differences were observed in the changes in the Ca/P ratio between the main group and the control group of children and adolescents in the study; a significant increase was observed in the CG-1 and CG-3 groups compared with the corresponding values of the Ca/P ratios. No statistically significant changes were found in MG-1 and CG-2 (n=0.146), while MG-3 showed an increase of almost 35% compared to that expected for this age group. In the study of the acid-base environment of the oral fluid, it was observed in negative changes in its pH-environment and buffer capacity - it was reflected in a decrease in the pH-environment, that is, in the group with cerebral palsy, the decrease in the pH-environment compared to the reference values of the corresponding age ranges was 12% in CG-3 and CG it was 14% at -2. In our opinion, this pathogenetic mechanism is buffer system imbalance; Not only is it related to the reduction of ionic components that regulate the pH-environment, but the

unstimulated secretion is also directly related to the decrease in the rate of salivary secretion [15]. Exactly, the examined button is directly related to the increased viscosity of oral fluid in all age groups of people with cerebral palsy. We also know that free radicals increase in the oral fluid when the pro-oxidant system is disturbed, which may be related to the loss of cytokines in the increase of long-term dental diseases, and significant reduction of anti-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokine modification products in the main group of patients with low molecular binding of local anti-inflammatory cytokines. is confirmed by the increase in level [16]. Compared to the control group, the significant predominance of anti-inflammatory cytokine processes and oral thrush indicate the vulnerability of biomolecules in the oral fluid; also, the content of anti-inflammatory cytokine modification products in MG-2 is 40% higher than in MG-1, which is reflected in the deterioration of oxidative modification as the duration of the disease increases in children [17]. Free radical oxidation is intensive in all groups, including age-matched increases in chemiluminescence compared to reference values. In addition, maximum chemiluminescence flash rates in older adolescents were significantly higher in the primary group than in the control group, in contrast to the younger age groups.

Compared to the control group between the age group MG-1 and MG-2, the main group showed a long-term attenuation, and the chemiluminescence area increased by 48-50% compared to CG-1 and CG-2. When analyzing the integral index, which reflects the performance of the prooxidant system-antioxidant system low molecular coupling, it was found that it was significantly increased in patients of all groups [18]. An increase in the indicator of the additional integral coefficient of the oxidative modification of biomolecules indicates the adaptive tension of the compensatory mechanisms of the antioxidant system, and its increase by more than 0.5-0.8 units should be considered as an

unfavorable prognostic sign, which indicates the oxidative decompensation of uncontrolled processes at the local level. In turn, the decrease in myeloperoxidase activity in the control group indicates a decompensation in the work of the first line of defense against microbes, which is especially evident when comparing these indicators with the average values in the control group [19]. However, the level of myeloperoxidase activity in oral fluid was lower in MG-1 and 2 compared to CG-1, and in MG-3 these differences were even greater, reflecting a more pronounced decompensation of local homeostasis. The results can be explained by a decrease in the functional capacity of neutrophil granulocytes, monocytes and macrophages during chronic infection at the local level against the background of prolonged systemic disease.

Superoxide dismutase activity was observed to increase in all groups relative to age-matched values; the biggest differences were noted in MG-2 and CG-2 groups. Disruption of permeability of the blood-saliva barrier against the background of decompensation of the systemic pathological process in patients with cerebral palsy, the peculiarity of the functioning of the antioxidant enzyme unit in physiological conditions can be explained by its interaction between the main enzymes [20]. The coordination of all components of the local non-specific resistance, including pro-inflammatory cytokines and anti-inflammatory and immune components is able to maintain the homeostasis of the oral cavity. Specifically, the integrated index of activity of antiradical protective oral fluid enzymes was significantly decreased in children with cerebral palsy compared to their corresponding values ($n < 0.05$). No statistically significant differences were detected in CG patients compared to age-specific reference values in integrated indicators of antiradical protection enzyme activity.

In the main group of patients in the study group, a slightly higher amount of IL-1 production was observed in the oral fluid, which, in our opinion, confirmed the leading role of the cytokine cascade in the oral mucosa, increasing not only its own synthesis, but also the increase of IL-6 and IL-8 and the activity of necrosis factors. A decrease in the concentration of IL-4 in local factors was observed due to an unfavorable factor, and a long-term increase in the synthesis of IL-1 created a factor for the chronic nature of inflammation. When comparing age groups, it can be observed that IL-1 increases more intensively in MG than in CG. An intensive increase in the amount of IL-8 was confirmed to be associated with the observation of granulocytic tissues with infiltration complications in the mucous membrane of the oral cavity. At the same time, it is confirmed that the formation of IL-8 in the inflammatory site begins after the increase in the amount of IL-1 necrosis factors and can cause the formation of a local autoimmune process. Concentrations of IL-10 and IL-4 are also observed to increase with increasing age in the main group of patients; this situation suggests an additive and synergistic relationship between IL-10 and IL-4 in immune formation. Cytokines - IL-1, IL-2, IL-4, IL-8 and IL-10 are considered for the formation of immunity, innate and adaptive immunity in them; that is, if under the influence of IL-1 we observe the production of IL-2 along with antigen degradation products in T-helper cells, at the same time T-lymphocytes play an important role in activating the growth of necrotic process in cells. Therefore, among the main group of patients, especially in older age groups, there is a significant difference in the amount of anti-inflammatory cytokines and anti-inflammatory agents in oral fluid (Table 2).

Table 2.

Low molecular binding state, balance of pro- and antioxidant system enzymes and IL content in oral fluid of patients of different ages.

Indicator	Clinical group (M ± σ)							
	Average MG	MG-1	MG -2	MG -3	Average CG	CG-1	CG -2	CG -3
S-XL, sh.b.	0,315±0,042*,#	0,234±0,047*	0,322±0,044*,#	0,389±0,044*,#	0,204±0,048^	0,171±0,044	0,198±0,022^	0,244±0,040^
Max BXL, sh.b.	0,218±0,034*,#	0,122±0,056	0,245±0,061*,#	0,288±0,022*,#	0,101±0,028	0,084±0,014	0,110±0,042	0,111±0,014
SH-group, opt. b.	0,032±0,006*	0,040±0,008*	0,036±0,002*	0,022±0,008*	0,030±0,002^	0,040±0,006	0,030±0,008^	0,024±0,003^
POM, opt. b.	0,232±0,022*,#	0,144±0,043*	0,228±0,042*,#	0,324±0,034*,#	0,123±0,045^	0,054±0,043	0,147±0,030^	0,168±0,060^
CAT, mmol·min ⁻¹ ·l ⁻¹ /(1mg/prot.)	40,2±4,38*,#	44,2±4,02*	39,8±4,78*,#	36,5± 4,78*,#	31,1±4,02	34,2±4,56	30,4±4,22	28,8±5,43
MPO, act. b.	2,70±0,44*,#	3,27±0,71*	2,69±0,25*,#	2,14±0,22*,#	6,00±0,44^	4,58±0,47	6,46±0,49^	6,98±0,49^
SOD, b.·l ⁻¹ /(1 mg prot.)	35,5±3,68*,#	31,8±4,2*	35,8±3,44*,#	38,8±2,4*,#	17,9±1,98	19,8±1,40	17,6±1,94	16,2±2,11
IL-1, ng/l	45,7±4,4*,#	41,4±4,8*	44,8±5,6*,#	45,8±3,8*,#	34,06±4,4^	29,4±4,5	34,6±4,8^	38,2±4,6^
IL-2, ng/l	86,1±10,6*,#	65,1±8,3*	94,7±10,9*,#	98,4±12,9*,#	54,9±6,8^	41,8±5,6	58,2±6,4^	64,8±7,5^
IL-8, ng/l	121,7±13,4*,#	104,4± 12,4*	129,4±14,2*,#	131,2±14,8*,#	87,5±11,6^	81,8±10,4	88,4±11,4^	92,2±13,5^
IL-4, ng/l	18,5±2,8*,#	16,8±3,4*	18,8±2,6*,#	19,8±2,9*,#	10,6±2,4^	12,8±2,4	10,6±2,2^	8,4±2,1^
IL-10, ng/l	12,4±2,1*,#	9,8±1,8*	12,8±2,2*,#	14,6±2,4*,#	6,2±1,3	5,2±1,4	6,4±1,4	6,9±1,2

Note: * - p<0.05 compared to the CG indicator of the corresponding age range; ^ - p<0.05 compared to the indicator of group 1; # - p < 0.05 compared to MG-1 indicator; conditional units - optical units; CAT - catalase; MPO - myeloperoxidase; SOD - superoxide dismutase; IL - interleukin.

Conclusions. Thus, in patients with cerebral palsy, a decrease in the parameters of unstimulated salivary secretion leads to pathological "hypersalivation", the process is a symptom of interrelationship with anatomical and functional disorders in organs and tissues - that is, swallowing disorders, hypofunction of the muscles of the oral cavity, pathologies in the tooth enamel, changes in the shape of the palate, dysfunctions of the autonomic nervous system, and others. In children and adolescents with cerebral palsy, the amount of P in oral fluid is sharply reduced by two times compared to CG; Differences in changes in Ca/P values between MG and CG; - sharply observed when comparing between CG-1 and CG-3 groups, but no statistically significant differences were observed between MG-1 and MG-2 (n=0.146); intensity of formation of free radicals, reactive molecules in the oral fluid of all other MG groups; It was noted that the pro-oxidant system reflects the low molecular binding of anti-inflammatory cytokines, especially as the age groups grow, the expression of superoxide dismutase prevents inflammation and anti-inflammatory cytokines. In children and adolescents with cerebral palsy, there are significant disturbances in the system that regulates the homeostasis of the tissues of the oral cavity and oral fluid, and this is organically related to the pathological processes in the area of the maxillofacial system. Also, among the children and adolescents in the control group with inflammation in the oral cavity, significant negative conditions were observed in the enzymatic and low molecular units of the antioxidant system, in the metabolism of minerals, and in the indicators of the immune system in the oral fluid - at the same time as the dysfunction of genetic significance, especially in older people with cerebral palsy. The clinical description of bilateral direct intensive aggravation between dental diseases in groups confirms the leadership.

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